

Kinetics of Oxidation of Propiophenone by Vanadium(v) in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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The kinetic investigations of the oxidation of propiophenone have been carried out in 60% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid medium. Order of reaction has been found to be unity with respect to oxidant, substrate and perchloric acid concentrations. No significant effect of the ionic strength has been observed. Studies with varying compositions of binary mixture of acetic acid and water have indicated the reaction to be ion-dipole type. Solvent isotopic effect reveals that the oxidant attacks on keto form rather than the enol form of the ketone, and suitable mechanistic steps involving free radical have been proposed. The thermodynamic parameters are also reported.

QUINQUEVALENT vanadium has been used under acid conditions, as an oxidant for various types of compounds¹. Kinetics of oxidation of ketones specifically aromatic ketones by vanadium(v) have not been much investigated. The initial work on acetophenone oxidation by vanadium(v) was done by Mishra *et al.*². They suggested a direct attack on keto form with benzoic acid as an end-product without the involvement of free radical and intermediate complex formation. No worthwhile conclusions can be drawn unless the whole class of compounds are studied systematically in their oxidation by this potent oxidant. It was, therefore, thought proper to investigate oxidation of propiophenone of this class. A suitable mechanism involving the free radical via intermediate complex formation has been suggested.

Experimental

The propiophenone was prepared³ and its purity checked. The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Ammonium metavanadate (Rediel) was used.

250 ml of each solutions used in kinetic run were pre-heated in a thermostat to attain thermostatic conditions. A requisite volume of substrate solution was quickly mixed with oxidant solution and acid solution in reaction flask and was made upto 30 ml with acetic acid - water binary mixture. The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously and aliquots (2.0 ml) withdrawn at regular intervals of time were quenched in ice-cold (2-4°) titration flask containing 5 M H₂SO₄ (10.0 ml) to arrest the reaction. The progress of the reaction was monitored by estimating the unconsumed oxidant titrimetrically by standard Mohr's salt solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic studies were performed by taking sufficient excess of [ketone] over [vanadium(v)]. It was observed that the rate of disappearance of vanadium(v) followed first order kinetics. The pseudo-first order rate constants k_{obs} were evaluated from the integrated form of first order rate equation. The values of rate constants k_{obs} were corrected by least-square method.

Addition of vanadium(v) ions cause a retarding effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). The decrease may be due to the formation of inactive V^V species, such as polymers of V^V. The kinetic data also reveal the dependence of rate on [ketone] (Table 2). The order in the ketone is found to be one. Moreover, a plot of k_{obs}^{-1} vs [ketone]⁻¹ was a straight line with positive intercept on the k_{obs}^{-1} axis, indicating thereby an intermediate complex formation between vanadium(v) and ketone. It has also been confirmed by conductometric methods.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [VV]

[Propiophenone] = 5.0×10^{-3} M, [HClO₄] = 9.0×10^{-1} M, AcOH = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 40°

[VV] × 10 ⁴ M	2.0	4.0	6.0	10.0
$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	10.46	8.81	7.16	8.88

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [PROPIOPHENONE]

[VV] = 6.0×10^{-4} M, [HClO₄] = 9.0×10^{-1} M, AcOH = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 40°

[Propiophenone] × 10 ³ M	1.0	5.0	9.0	14.0	20.0
$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	3.42	7.16	13.57	14.64	15.44

The results (Table 3) of the oxidation at various [HClO₄] show first order dependence of rate on

acid concentration. No primary kinetic salt effect has been observed on the addition of NaClO₄ (Table 4) which shows that the reaction ought to be between neutral molecule and ion as reported earlier^{3,5}. However at a fixed [ClO₄⁻] of 0.5 M, there is slight increase in the reaction rate when [HClO₄] was varied (Table 5). The reaction has been found to obey the Arrhenius relationship over the range studied. The values of thermodynamic parameters are recorded in Table 6.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [HClO₄]

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, AcOH = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 40°

[HClO ₄] M	0.1	0.5	0.9	1.4	2.0
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	5.40	6.93	7.16	10.50	24.19

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [ClO₄⁻]

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [HClO₄] = 9.0 × 10⁻¹ M, AcOH = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 40°

[ClO ₄ ⁻] M	0.2	0.6	0.8	1.0
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	7.47	7.43	7.48	7.60

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [H⁺] AT CONSTANT [ClO₄⁻]

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [ClO₄⁻] = 0.5 M, AcOH = 60% (v/v), Temp. = 40°

[HClO ₄] M	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	2.61	5.25	6.03	7.00	9.39

TABLE 6—REACTION RATE AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [HClO₄] = 9.0 × 10⁻¹ M, AcOH = 60% (v/v)

Temp. (K)	308	318	318	328
k ₂ × 10 ³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ min ⁻¹	8.73	14.32	19.49	32.47

ΔE = 17.73 kcal mol⁻¹, PZ = 8.02 × 10¹⁰ mol⁻¹ dm³ min⁻¹, ΔS[‡] = -7.90 e.u.

It has been observed that the rate constant increases inversely with dielectric constant of the medium (Table 7). A linear plot of log k_{obs} vs D⁻¹ with a positive slope shows the reaction to be of ion-dipole type⁶. It can be assumed that ketone molecules behave as dipole in acetic acid medium whereas positive ionic species of V^V may be considered to be active in the reaction.

TABLE 7—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF MEDIUM

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [HClO₄] = 9.0 × 10⁻¹ M, Temp. = 40°

% AcOH (v/v)	60	64	68	76	80
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	7.16	9.66	11.59	13.20	15.20
D ⁻¹ × 10 ³	29.65	32.66	35.79	41.74	45.00

The rate coefficient of the oxidation, both in D₂O and H₂O (Table 8) shows that if the isotopic effect was due to a rate-determining enolisation step, it would be expected to be the same as that

observed for the acid enolisation. k_{D₂O}/k_{H₂O} > 2 clearly indicates that the vanadium(V) attacks keto form⁷ rather than the enol form of the propiophenone.

TABLE 8—SOLVENT ISOTOPE EFFECT ON REACTION RATE AT 40°

[Propiophenone] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, [VV] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [HClO₄] = 9.0 × 10⁻¹ M, AcOH = 60% (v/v)

k _{H₂O} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k _{D₂O} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k _{D₂O} /k _{H₂O}
7.16	14.33	2.00

Vanadium(V) in aqueous acidic medium has been described as VO₂⁺ (aq.)⁸. This form can change in different types of acids and their concentration ranges. In the present case the protonated species⁹ like V(OH)₂²⁺ has been considered as active one as rate is influenced by [H⁺] (Table 5).

The involvement of such type of charged species V(OH)₂²⁺ is further supported by the data obtained by changing the percentage composition of binary mixture of acetic acid - water (Table 7).

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be six moles of V^V to one mole of the ketone. The benzoic acid was the end-product of the oxidation reaction. The formation of free radical was confirmed by the induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile and mercuric chloride reduction test.

Mechanism: From the kinetic data, product analysis and the foregoing discussion the possible mechanism of oxidation could be represented as

On this basis, the disappearance of vanadium(V) with time at constant [HClO₄] can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_s [\text{Complex}] \\ &= k_s K [V^V][S] \end{aligned}$$

substituting for [V^V]_T, the rate law reduces to

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = \frac{K k_s [V^V]_T [S]}{1 + K[S]}$$

and under the condition of kinetic run when [Substrate] >> [vanadium(V)] as

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = k_{obs} [V^V]_T \quad (4)$$

From equations (3) and (4) it follows that

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K k_s [S]}{1 + K[S]} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) explains all the observed results, thus supporting the assumptions made in arriving at the mechanism (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

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